

Energy harvesting from robot vibrations by means of piezoelectric devices

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Abstract—In this paper, the possibility of using piezoelectric energy harvesting technologies on an industrial Delta robot is investigated. In particular, a typical trajectory of the robot is analyzed both in the time and frequency domain in order to properly tune the harvester. Then, the voltage signal generated by the harvester mounted on the end effector of the robot is investigated by means of preliminary experimental tests. Results are discussed and future possible developments are presented.

Index Terms—Piezoelectric harvester, Robot vibrations, Robot trajectory.

I. INTRODUCTION

This paper deals with the novel application of piezoelectric harvesters in the field of robotic manipulators. The piezoelectric harvesters could be adopted to feed sensors mounted on the end effector of the robot reducing the need of wiring to the robot controller. High-speed robot motions are characterized by high accelerations that could be used to excite the first mode of vibration of a cantilever piezoelectric harvester. Delta robots, known for their rapid and precise positioning in pick-and-place operations [1], [2], are ideal for energy harvesting due to their high accelerations.

II. EXPERIMENTAL EQUIPMENT

In the framework of this research the Delta robot by Adept depicted in Figure 1a was used. The robot was equipped with a monoaxial accelerometer PCB Model 608A11 mounted on a stiff part of the end effector. The acceleration was acquired along the x -axis of the robot. Then, the end effector was equipped with a commercial cantilever harvester M2814P2C-01 made by Smart Material GmbH with tip mass [4]. The detail of the setup is reported in Figure 1b. Voltage and acceleration signals were acquired using a sampling rate of 2048 Hz and a number of samples equal to 8192.

III. FREQUENCY DOMAIN ANALYSIS OF THE TRAJECTORY

First, a typical trajectory for a simple pick-and-place task was planned. The trajectory lies in the $x - z$ plane, the

Fig. 1: (a) Delta robot by Adept used for the experiments; (b) Monoaxial accelerometer and piezoelectric cantilever harvester M2814P2C-01 mounted on the end effector of the robot.

motion time was set equal to ≈ 0.45 s. The coordinates of the trajectory are listed in Table I. The trajectory is depicted in Figure 2.

Points	x (mm)	y (mm)	z (mm)
A	-300	0	-950
B	-300	0	-800
C	300	0	-800
D	300	0	-950

TABLE I: Coordinates of the points of the trajectory.

Fig. 2: Scheme of the experimental pick-and-place trajectory.

Fig. 3: (a) Experimental accelerations acquired during the tests along the x axis; (b) FFT of the experimental accelerations along x -axis.

The acceleration of the end effector of the robot was acquired by means of the accelerometer. The same trajectory was repeated 5 times, and Figure 3a shows a good repeatability of the measured acceleration. The maximum acceleration value is around $4g$.

In order to properly tune the harvester, it is necessary to analyze the frequency content of the trajectory. The single trajectory depicted in Figure 2, from point A to point D, can be considered as a transient signal. This signal can be analyzed in the frequency domain using fast Fourier transform (FFT).

The result of the FFT calculation is depicted in Figure 3b.

It is not possible to tune the harvester to the first or second peak of the FFT because in these cases very large tip masses would be necessary to lower the natural frequencies of the harvester. Therefore, a tip mass of $66g$ was attached to the tip of the energy harvester to lower the resonance frequency to the third harmonic of FFT ($\approx 15Hz$) see Figure 3b.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL TESTS OF THE PIEZOELECTRIC CANTILEVER HARVESTER ON THE ROBOT'S END EFFECTOR

The piezoelectric harvester was mounted on the end effector of the robot (as depicted in Figure 1b), and the trajectory described in Section III (from point A to D) was performed 5 times in different tests. The generated open-circuit (OC) voltage was recorded by means of a NI9230 board, able to acquire signals up to $30V$. The OC voltage is an important factor in the design of specific electronic circuits for energy storage and load supply. The results are depicted in Figure 4.

Fig. 4: Voltage generated by the piezoelectric harvester subjected to the trajectory presented in Section III.

The FFT of the measured OC voltage ($\mathcal{F}\{v(t)\}(\omega)$) is depicted in Figure 5.

Fig. 5: FFT of the voltage generated by the piezoelectric harvester subjected to the trajectory presented in Section III.

The Root Mean Square (RMS) of the generated voltage can be calculated according to the Parseval's theorem.

The RMS of the generated voltage is about $6.1V$, and it is enough to open the possibility of feeding small sensors or controlling boards, like Arduino Nano or similar.

The transfer function ($H(\omega)$) between the voltage generated by the harvester and the base acceleration can be obtained by means of the independent tests [3] and it is useful to predict the behavior of the harvester with different trajectories.

The FFT of the voltage generated by the harvester in the frequency domain ($\mathcal{F}\{v(t)\}(\omega)$), subjected to a specific trajectory, can be calculated as:

$$\mathcal{F}\{v(t)\}(\omega) = H(\omega)\mathcal{F}\{\ddot{x}_e(t)\}(\omega) \quad (1)$$

As depicted in Figure 5, there is a good agreement between the calculated $\mathcal{F}\{v(t)\}(\omega)$ and the FFT of the experimentally generated voltage.

V. CONCLUSION

The possibility of using piezoelectric energy harvesters in the field of industrial robotics was investigated. Experimental tests showed that the RMS voltage generated is enough to feed small electronic circuits.

Future developments of this paper will include further analysis of different trajectories, and an optimization process to properly tune the harvester and maximize the generated voltage.

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